

ISic0156

I.Sicily inscription 0156

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) [M(anibus)]

2. Copo[ni][---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Copo[ni---].

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493964

EDCS 10900649

Bibliography

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Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.

Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 77
Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 264 no.28c

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